

**DEVELOPMENT OF ANALYTICAL SCIENTIFIC APPROACHES TO
THE LOCOMOTIVE REPAIR SYSTEM**

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Abstract: Currently it has become the main issue to determine the condition and repair of locomotive traction electric motors in the exploitation period, as well as to extend the service life. This results in an additional cost. Therefore, to divide the parts of locomotives into following groups while repair and technical service: - traction electric motors; - auxiliary electric machines; - electric circuits and devices; - electronic equipment; - safety devices; - management system; - pneumatic equipment; - mechanical part and to analyze extensively the malfunctions of the equipment might increase effective use of electric locomotive engines and the efficiency of locomotives in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Locomotives, mechanical part, failure flow parameter, repair component, traction motors.

Introduction

The operation of locomotives is the main link in the organization of train traffic, ensuring that activities related to the use of locomotives on railway lines, their maintenance, repair and preparation for use are carried out.

When organizing the operation of locomotives, the Basic Rules, procedure and locomotive brigades for the use of locomotives are established, as well as personnel associated with the organization of operational management of the locomotive fleet.

Measures that ensure the operation of locomotives, including optimal operation, include: Organization of locomotive work; daily, monthly and annual normalization of locomotive fleet work; network [12].

Analysis of recent research and problem statement

Eight locomotives to ensure the sustainable operation of the society maintenance and current repair of locomotives and MVHT in depots a repair-warning system is being implemented.

At the “Uztemiryo‘lmashta‘mir” UP, locomotives are perfectly repaired and restoration works are being carried out by extending their service life.

By the end of 2022, Sections of 87 locomotives according to repair types CR-1, CR-2 have been completely repaired.

In 2023, 78 locomotive sections for these types of repairs are intended to carry out perfect repair work.

Table-1

Repair and technical service types which are carried out in “Uzbekistan Railways” JSC locomotive depots and “Uztemiryo‘lmashta‘mir” UP [12]

Locomotive depot and Factory	Repair and technical service types which are carried out in “Uzbekistan Railways” JSC								
	Technical service			CurR			CR		ECR
	TS-2	TS-3	TS-4	Cur R-1	Cur R-1r	Cur R-3	CR-1	CR-2	ECR
Uzbekistan	++*	+	+	+	+	+	+	-*	-
Kokand	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
Tinchlik	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
Bukhara	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
Kungirat	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
Karshi	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
Termiz	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
Urgench	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
“Uztemiryo‘lmashta‘mir” UP	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+

Notes: * “+” performed services (works), “-” not performed works (services);

According to the contract No. PIU-05 dated July 17, 2019, 22 freight electric locomotives and 8 freight and passenger electric locomotives were in exploitation [1-3].

Traction electric motors

As a result of changes in atmosphere and temperature electrical devices of electric locomotives, especially traction electric motors, work in very complex conditions. In addition, they are able to withstand the dynamic effects that may occur due to unevenness of the road during movement and during acceleration and boxing, as well as short-term overloads due to frequent changes in the operating mode. When the cooling system malfunctions and when the ambient temperature is high, the insulation dries out, cracks appear, and as a result, it can leak. At low temperatures, when the electrical components are stopped for a long time, moisture occurs or freezes in the collector, and oil condenses on the bearings and their tops. Traction electric motors (TEM) are affected by large dynamic effects, especially at high speeds, which can cause cracks, erosion of friction surfaces, and loosening of bolted joints in nodes.

Auxiliary electric machines

Electrical (current-conducting) parts of locomotive equipment include conductors, letter contact connections and current-conducting insulation. The normal operation of locomotives depends on the electrical equipment as well as the mechanical parts of the electrical equipment. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure the safety of the mechanical equipment in advance or spare parts. Insulation, conductors and cables, traverses, brush brackets and other marking correction works are also included.

Fig.-1. Traction motor repair flow line [8]

I - parting line; II - saturation section; III - assembly line; IV – anchors repair line; 1.17 - position of defecting; 2 - disassembly position; 3 - spraying chamber; 4 - motor cantor; 5 - mechanical part repair position; 6, 23 - transport

carts; 7 - welding post; 8 - electrical insulation stability check position; 9 - the position of collecting the ostov; electric circuits and devices. 10 – brush position of installation of handles; 11 - motor assembly position; 12 - test of engine operation stand; 13 - testing station; 14 - motor anchor; 15 - spraying chamber; 16 - anchor anchor; 18 - balancing lathe; 19 - a machine for welding collector ends; 20,22,26, 28 - accumulators; 21.27 - repair and inspection positions of the anchor electric part; 24, 25 - machines for opening and grinding the collector.

Electronic equipment

Various diagnostic devices are used to check the condition of the magnet system of Ostov and Yakor. There are a number of tools available to determine the windings in the main and auxiliary pole windings. The common feature in their design and operation is the supply of alternating current to the chain of the main and additional poles of the motor. With the help of a measuring device, the EYUK indicators are obtained at the pole. A short circuit between the windings can be effectively detected using an A-1941 pulse device. when using this device, a non-alternating, but 50 Hz pulsed voltage with a duration of 200 μ s is transmitted to the pole chain. In this case, the number of rolls of measuring tape should be more. A KPEM device has also been developed for checking DC electric machines. This tool allows you to determine the connection between the coils in the coils of the anchor, main and additional poles, the connection in the magnetic system of 273 ostov, and set the handles of the motor brush to the geometric neutral. The insulation resistance of traction motors or auxiliary machines is measured in most depots with 2.5 kV or 0.5 kV megohmmeters, where the armature is turned by hand through a gear.

Safety devices

According to their purpose, electrical devices are divided into control, automatic adjustment and protection devices. In the process of use, electrical devices are subject to dynamic and electrodynamic effects, as well as changes in ambient temperature. In addition, the performance of devices depends on their level of humidity and contamination. As a result of the above-mentioned effects, malfunctions such as

burning and melting of contacts and copper shunts, damage to coils, reduction of insulation properties, and air leakage in conducting nodes occur in the nodes and details of devices. In order to ensure that the devices are in correct and reliable condition during the period of use and during the technical inspection, their nodes and elements are regularly cleaned, the tightness of threaded connections is checked, the corresponding nodes are lubricated, the condition of the insulation and the reliability of the devices are checked.

Pneumatic equipment

In the course of use, the correct pneumatic lubrication is determined by the accuracy of operation and the loss of air in the sealing joints. If the density is disturbed, it can be eliminated by adding 1-6 cm³ of antifreeze oil or by tightening the bolts or replacing the sealing gaskets. During the repair, pneumatic tires are disassembled, and after cleaning, the main parts and components are measured, the condition of the surfaces is inspected, possible cracks in the cylinder body are identified, and the pistons are checked for residual deformation. If there are scratches on the working surfaces of the cylinders, they are polished, if the increase in diameter is more than 0.5 mm, they are replaced or galvanically restored. Damaged rubber cuffs are replaced with new ones, and leather cuffs are restored by oiling in a thermostat at a temperature of 60 oC for 3-4 hours. Cracks and grooves in the cylinder body are eliminated by welding with brass electrodes. It is allowed to eliminate small defects with BF-2 glue or epoxy composition.

Mechanical part.

Preventive work on checking the condition of the locomotive's crew, lubrication, measuring gaps, etc., is carried out during the period of technical services and current maintenance in the scope of CurR-1. During the current maintenance period of the CurR-1k electric motors, motor-shaft bearings and torque reducers are revised with the lower part of the box removed, and the bushings are also checked. In the current repair of the CurR -3 size, bogies are removed from under the locomotive and bogie frames, spring suspension, wheel pairs, bushings, etc. are repaired [8].

The purpose and tasks of the study

During the registration of the malfunction, the total was fixed mileage of the electric locomotive on which the malfunction was detected, from construction and from appropriate type of maintenance or current repair. Electric locomotives and their equipment, from the point of view of reliability, are devices that are restored, that is, in the event of a malfunction, equipment is sent for repair, where its serviceability is restored and working capacity. In this way, it is assumed that there will be no electric locomotives only in good and bad condition as provided for non-renewable devices, but also being under repairs (planned and unscheduled), awaiting repair, in the state of transportation for execution repair, transportation after repair, etc [8-11].

Materials and methods of research

As the main the reliability index of nodes that are renewable is used the probability of failure-free operation $P(t)$ during the interval t . As an interval operation time or mileage may be accepted. Since for electric locomotives, it is customary to calculate work intervals in units linear mileage, and not in calendar calculation (with the exception of technical maintenance TO-2), reliability indicators are reduced to mileage electric locomotives in kilometers. In the case of determining the probability dependence uptime, uptime parameter was denoted as $P(L)$. In addition to the probability of trouble-free operation, significant are indicators of the average working time for the failure of certain TV nodes, failure flow parameter $\omega(L)$. The average value of the failure flow parameter nodes $\omega_{cp}(L)$ for the mileage of the electric locomotive was determined by statistical methods

$$\omega_{cp}(L) = \frac{\sum_1^{N_0} m_k(L+\Delta L) - \sum_1^{N_0} m_k(L)}{\Delta L N_0} \quad (1)$$

The failure flow parameter of the electric locomotive as a whole as a system equipment and nodes of various types was defined as

$$\Omega(L) = \frac{\Delta m_e}{\Delta L} \frac{1}{N_e} \quad (2)$$

Where $\Delta m_e = \sum_{n=1}^{N_e} m_i$ – is the total number of electric locomotives located in exploitation;

N_e is the number of operated fleet of electric locomotives, which are operated on the segment ΔL .

During reliability calculations of renewable nodes and electric locomotives in general, failure flow is usually considered simple. Such an assumption justified by the fact that renewable nodes, and even more so electric locomotive as a whole, consist of a large number of nodes, parameters flow of failures which are small, they all have one order and each of them does not separately define the failure flow parameter of the node as a whole. Considering electric locomotive as a system consisting of N different renewable nodes purpose, the probability of its trouble-free operation was presented in the form.

$$P(L) = e^{-\omega_1 L} e^{-\omega_2 L} \dots e^{-\omega_N L} = e^{-L \sum_1^N \omega_i} = e^{-\Omega L} \quad (3)$$

Where does the failure flow parameter of the electric locomotive come from

$$\Omega = \omega_1 + \omega_2 + \dots + \omega_N = \sum_1^N \omega_i \quad (4)$$

As a result of calculations according to (1 – 4), quantitative values were obtained reliability characteristics by types of equipment (table -2) for the first five years of their operation.

Table-2.

Quantitative characteristics of equipment reliability

Type of equipment	Number refusal, vol.	Parameter rejection flow, km^{-1}	Center scattering refusals, thousand km
Traction engines	13	$0,86 \cdot 10^{-7}$	545.75
Auxiliary electric machines	36	$1,4 \cdot 10^{-7}$	503.26
Electric circuits and devices	11	$0,39 \cdot 10^{-7}$	444.15
Electronic Equipment	11	$0,52 \cdot 10^{-7}$	372.72
Pneumatic equipment	19	$0,34 \cdot 10^{-7}$	343.0
Mechanical part	15	$0,4 \cdot 10^{-7}$	504.25

The analysis of the obtained results indicates insufficient reliability of the new ones electric locomotives. In particular, auxiliary ones were most often damaged electric machines, pneumatic equipment and mechanical elements parts. Given the age of electric locomotives, we can say that the majority damage caused by structural defects. Frequent refusals in operation of asynchronous electric motors of the NVA-55 type for driving the compressor occur due to design imperfections.

Unreliability of the design driver's crane No.130 and automatic brake control devices. This also explains the constant failures of electropneumatics control valves, pressure switch RD3, electronic boards and electrical installation wires. A vulnerable point in the operation of electric locomotives 2EL5 and 2ES5K failure of compressors due to damage plate valves [4-7].

As a result of processing statistical data on malfunctions electric locomotives as a whole were found to be the most frequent group of equipment fail. A third of the failures in the fleet of electric locomotives are accounted for auxiliary electric machines. 10-25% of failures are mechanical part. About 20% of failures are due to pneumatic equipment. Traction failure engines for five years of operation increased from 5% to 50%. The general parameter of the failure flow of electric locomotives was 6.5310-7 km-1.

3. Conclusion

However, it is important to emphasize that an increase in the failure flow parameter period of operations which were analyzed in the beginning of the study indicates the negative impact of the repair component. That requires further approach and new innovations in inadequate facilities of technological preparation of repair production depot for the repair of new equipment.

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